

Description and Manual of the *SensOr Interfacing Language*

Version 2.3.0

27.06.2024

Matthias Bodenbenner

Technical Manual

Intelligence in Quality Sensing
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Robert Schmitt

WZL | RWTH Aachen University
Campus-Boulevard 30
52074 Aachen

Contents

Listings	5
License	7
Changelog	9
I The SensOr Interfacing Language	11
1 Introduction	13
2 Basics	15
2.1 Terms	15
2.1.1 Elements of SensOr Interfacing Language (SOIL)	15
2.1.2 Terms of Computer Science Theory	16
2.2 Model	17
2.3 Enums	18
2.4 Using controlled terms	18
3 Parts of SOIL Models	19
3.1 Parts	19
3.2 Variables	19
3.2.1 Datatypes	21
3.2.2 Dimension	21
3.2.3 Range	21
3.3 Functions	22
3.4 Components	23
3.4.1 Defining default values of <i>parameters</i>	24
3.4.2 Overriding meta-information	25
3.4.3 Constant parameters	26
3.4.4 Streaming functions	27
3.4.5 Dynamic components	27
3.4.6 Extending components	28
3.4.7 Internal measurements	28
3.5 Interfaces	29
4 Using controlled terms	31
4.1 Units	31
4.2 Targeting controlled terms	32

5	Advanced features	33
5.1	Events	33
5.2	Streams	34
5.2.1	Streaming measurements	35
5.2.2	Streaming from functions	35
5.3	List of variables	36
5.4	Imports	36
II	The Python Unified Device Interface	39
6	The Python Unified Device Interface	41
6.1	Implementation of a cyber-physical measurement system (CPMS) using SOIL in Python	41
6.1.1	The TOP-Mechanism	42
6.1.2	Implementation suggestions	43
6.2	Details on the programm flow of the CPMS implemented with Python Unified Device Interface (PUDI)	44
III	Annex	49
7	Examples	51
7.1	Virtual Environmental Monitoring System	51
7.2	Virtual Laser Tracker	53
7.3	Fictional Mobile Robot	58

Listings

2.1	Example of class and variable definitions in Python.	17
2.2	Example of <i>element type</i> and <i>element</i> definitions in SOIL.	17
2.3	Pseudo-definition of general structure of a SOIL file	17
2.4	Example of the definition and usage of an enum	18
3.1	Pseudo-definition of the basic structure of a SOIL <i>element type</i>	19
3.2	Example of well-defined variables	20
3.3	Example of well-defined functions	22
3.4	Example of well-defined components	23
3.5	Examples showing the override of default values of components	25
3.6	Examples of the override of meta-information	25
3.7	Examples of constant parameters	26
3.8	Examples of a dynamic child component	27
3.9	Examples of a dynamic child component	27
3.10	Examples of the extension mechanism for components	28
3.11	Examples of an interface	29
4.1	Example of definition prefixes	31
4.2	Example of a unit definition using controlled terms.	31
5.1	Informal definition of the syntax of events	34
5.2	Example of events	34
5.3	Example of streams	35
5.4	Example of a variable list.	36
5.5	Example for importing SOIL files - Part 1: File <i>base.soil</i>	36
5.6	Example for importing SOIL files - Part 2: File <i>exteions.soil</i> which is located in the same directory as the file <i>base.soil</i>	37
6.1	Generated Python class extended by the handwritten code (HWC)-class in Listing 6.2 to implement its logic.	42
6.2	HWC Python class implementing the logic of the extended, generated class in Listing 6.1.	42
6.3	Generated Python class extended by the HWC-class in Listing 6.4 to implement its logic.	42
6.4	HWC Python class implementing the logic of the extended, generated class in Listing 6.3.	42

6.5	Exemplary content of the file <code>main.py</code> for starting the CPMS based on the generated source code.	43
6.6	Example of wrapping the logic of the CPMS implemented in the <code>Device</code> class.	43
6.7	Example of a parameter of the CPMS which does not affect the devices logic, and can therefore be handled directly (and not in the <code>Device</code> class).	44
6.8	Very simple SOIL model having one variable and one component using this variable as measurement. Moreover, the component defines a fixed stream for this measurement.	45
6.9	The component class of the temperature sensor generated from the model in Listing 6.8.	45
6.10	The JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) serialization of the SOIL model of the temperature sensor as defined in Listing 6.8.	46
7.1	Full example of a fictional virtual environmental sensor system	51
7.2	"Main" SOIL model file "lasertracker.soil" containing the interface definition.	53
7.3	SOIL model file "base_stations.soil" which defines the base station of a laser tracker.	54
7.4	SOIL model file "mobile_entities.soil" which defines the mobile entities i.e. the targets of a laser tracker.	56
7.5	SOIL model file "utils.soil" contains utility elements used multiple other files of the example.	57
7.6	Full example of a fictional mobile robot i.e. a six-arm robot mounted on an AVG.	58

License

This documentation and the domain-specific language, the SensOr Interfacing Language (SOIL) described here is licensed under **CC BY-SA 4.0**.

You are free to:

Share - copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format

Adapt - remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms.

Under the following terms:

Attribution - You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

ShareAlike - If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.

No additional restrictions - You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

Notices:

You do not have to comply with the license for elements of the material in the public domain or where your use is permitted by an applicable exception or limitation.

No warranties are given. The license may not give you all the permissions necessary for your intended use. For example, other rights such as publicity, privacy, or moral rights may limit how you use the material.

Changelog

2.3.0 - 27.06.2024

- added `List` feature for variables

2.2.0 - 24.05.2024

- overriding meta-information now also works for arguments and returns of functions

2.1.0 - 22.05.2024

- changed syntax for "streaming" functions (cf. Section 3.4.4)
- fixed the definition of *Parameter* (cf. Definition 3)
- updated syntax highlighting to be aligned with the web editor

2.0.0 - 12.04.2024

- merged element types "measurement" and "parameter" to "variable"
- added semantics for functions
- added an explanation for development of SOIL-based measuring devices
- added an explanation for usage of the Python Unified Device Interface (PUDI)

1.1.0 - 07.02.2024

- introduction of using controlled terms
- added "internal" measurements
- added "streaming" functions

1.0.1 - 28.03.2023

- added changelog
- fixed many typos

1.0.0 - 22.03.2023

- initial version
- description of all basic features of SOIL

Part I

The SensOr Interfacing Language

This manual describes the syntax and semantics of a domain-specific modeling language for defining functionally modeled sensor interfaces, called *SensOr Interfacing Language (SOIL)*. The description is mainly based on hands-on examples instead of formal definitions.

If you have any questions, feel free to contact the author Matthias Bodenbenner.

Related publications

More information on and use cases of SOIL can be found in the following scientific publications:

Bodenbenner, M.; Sanders, M. P.; Montavon, B.; Schmitt, R. H. (2021): *Domain-Specific Language for Sensors in the Internet of Production*. In: Bernd-Arno Behrens, Alexander Brosius, Wolfgang Hintze, Steffen Ihlenfeldt und Jens Peter Wulfsberg (Hg.): Production at the leading edge of technology. Proceedings of the 10th Congress of the German Academic Association for Production Technology (WGP), Dresden, 23-24 September 2020. Berlin, Heidelberg, 2021. 1st ed. 2021. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer (Lecture Notes in Production Engineering), S. 448–456, http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-62138-7_45

Bodenbenner, M.; Montavon, B.; Schmitt, R.H. (2021): *FAIR sensor services - Towards sustainable sensor data management*. In: Measurement: Sensors 18, S. 100206, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2021.100206>

Montavon, B. (2021): *Virtual Reference Frame Based on Distributed Large-Scale Metrology Providing Coordinates as a Service*. Aachen: Apprimus Verlag, <https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2021-10238>

Montavon, B.; Peterek, M.; Schmitt, R. H. (2019): *Model-based interfacing of large-scale metrology instruments*. In: Ettore Stella (Hg.): Multimodal Sensing: Technologies and Applications. 26-27 June 2019, Munich, Germany. Multimodal Sensing and Artificial Intelligence: Technologies and Applications. Munich, Germany, 6/24/2019 - 6/27/2019. Bellingham, Washington: SPIE (Proceedings of SPIE. 5200-, volume 11059), S. 11, <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2527461>

Acknowledgements

Funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy – EXC-2023 Internet of Production – 390621612.

Funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Project-ID 432233186 – AIMS.

The first chapter defines some terms to avoid ambiguity and describes what a file that defines a SOIL model looks like and how enums are defined in SOIL.

2.1 Terms

For the sake of unambiguity, we defined some terms beforehand.

2.1.1 Elements of SOIL

Definition 1: Elements

Whenever we talk about *elements*, it can be any of these four:

- *measurement*,
- *parameter*,
- *function*,
- *component*.

If we talk about a *variable*, this element can either be a parameter or a measurement.

Definition 2: Measurement

Measurements are used as representatives for all information physically sensed by the measuring system. This information includes the intended purpose, like temperature or distances, but also information like battery level or signal strength. The inherited value cannot be altered externally in contrast to *parameters*.

Definition 3: Parameter

Parameters express properties of the measuring system. The value of a parameter can be nominal or quantifiable.

Definition 4: Function

Functions are used for triggering complex tasks or changing the inner state of the measuring system. A function generally expects a set of *arguments* and yields a set of *returns*.

Definition 5: Component

Components are structural elements of a SOIL interface. Each component contains an arbitrary number of children elements, so the overall model has a tree-like shape.

2.1.2 Terms of Computer Science Theory

Definition 6: Composition

Elements a component is composed of are called *children* of this component. The component an element composes is called *parent* of the element. Elements that are children of the same component are called *siblings*.

Definition 7: Inheritance

To precisely distinguish between the inheritance and composition relation of components: A component extending another component is called the *subcomponent* of this inheritance relation. A component extended by another Component is called the *base component* of this inheritance relation.

Definition 8: Element Types

Element types define the attributes of elements. There are three different kinds of *element types* in SOIL:

- *variable*,
- *function*,
- *component*.

Wherever a *child* of a component is defined, we define an *element* having a specific *element type*.

Info: Similarity to general-purpose languages (GPLs)

This distinction between *element types* and *elements* can be best understood when considering GPLs. The *element type* corresponds to the definition of a class (like in Python). The definition of an *element* inside *component* corresponds to the instantiation of a variable or attribute of that class somewhere else in the source code. (c.f. Listing 2.1, and Listing 2.2)

```

1 # Definition of the class 'Width' > Element type definition in
  SOIL
2 class Width(object):
3 def __init__(self, value: int):
4     self._value = value
5
6 # Definition of the class 'Cube' > Element type definition in
  SOIL
7 class Cube(object):
8     def __init__(self, value: int):
9         # Definition of a variable 'width' of the class 'Width'
  > Element definition in SOIL
10         self._width = Width(value)

```

Listing 2.1: Example of class and variable definitions in Python.

```

1 # Definition of element type 'Width' > class definition in
  Python
2 variable Width {
3     ...
4 }
5
6 # Definition of element type 'Cube' > class definition in Python
7 component Cube {
8     ...
9     measurements:
10         # Definition of element 'width' of element type 'Width'
  > variable definition in Python
11         Width width
12 }

```

Listing 2.2: Example of *element type* and *element* definitions in SOIL.

2.2 Model

A complete SOIL model can span across multiple files. Each file contains a set of *parts*. Those parts are type definitions of *enums*, *variables*, *functions*, *components* and the initialization of the *interface*.

The file starts with an arbitrary number of import and prefix statements. After the import and prefix statements, a file must contain at least one *part*.

```

1 ((import <import -name>;) | (@prefix <prefix>:<<URL>>;))*
2 (parts)+

```

Listing 2.3: Pseudo-definition of general structure of a SOIL file

We now start with the description of the parts of a SOIL model. How imports work in SOIL is described in Section 5.4.

2.3 Enums

Enum is one of the basic datatypes available in SOIL. Whenever the datatype of a variable type is `enum`, there is a specified list of permissible values the measurement or parameter can take. An *enum* must be defined beforehand to use it as the datatype of a measurement or parameter. The name of the *enum* is then assigned to the `range` attribute of the element. The syntax of *enums* is very simple:

```
1 enum State {
2     IDLE
3     BUSY
4     STOPPED
5 }
6
7 variable State {
8     name: "state"
9     description: "The general state of a component."
10    datatype: enum
11    dimension: []
12    range: State
13 }
```

Listing 2.4: Example of the definition and usage of an enum

Tip: Values of enums

Note that the permissible values of an enum must not necessarily be written in upper letters.

2.4 Using controlled terms

SOIL allows the use of terms defined in publicly available vocabularies, ontologies, or terminologies according to standards of the *semantic web*. For example, this is particularly useful to unambiguously define the unit of a *variable*, e.g., using terms from QUDT. A detailed explanation of using controlled terms can be found in Chapter 4.

Info: Using semantics is optional

It is not mandatory to use controlled terms. A SOIL model can be defined entirely without any controlled term. However, this reduces the expressiveness and interoperability of the defined data and sensor model. Moreover, generating a full description compliant with semantic web standards or metadata profiles of a SOIL model is impossible without adequately using the controlled terms.

Parts of SOIL Models

This chapter introduces the basic building blocks of a SOIL model.

3.1 Parts

There are five types of *parts*: `variable`, `function`, `component`, `enum` and `interface`. The most important ones are the three *element types* of a SOIL model: `variable`, `function`, and `component`. The definition of *element types* is of the following general form:

```
1 <type> Name {
2     (<attribute>: value)+
3 }
```

Listing 3.1: Pseudo-definition of the basic structure of a SOIL *element type*

`<type>` is one of the three keywords `variable`, `function` or `component`. The set of mandatory or optional `<attribute>` is explained for each element.

All *element types* have two mandatory attributes:

name : Human readable name of an *element type*. Value is of type "string".

description : Human-readable description to briefly describe the meaning or purpose of that *element type*. Value is of type "string".

In the following, we describe how the three *element types* must be defined. You can also switch to Enums (c.f. Section 2.3) and Interfaces (c.f. Section 3.5) if you are already familiar with the three *element type*.

3.2 Variables

A *Variable* is the *element type* for defining the attributes and characteristics of *measurements* and *parameters*

A variable has four to six attributes in arbitrary order (incl. `name` and `description`). Required attributes are:

datatype One of six "primitive" *datatypes* (c.f. Section 3.2.1) of SOIL. The data type is usually `int` or `float` for variables which are later instantiated as measurements.

dimension Mathematical *dimension* (c.f. Section 3.2.2) of the value, i.e., whether it is a scalar, vector, or matrix. However, matrices should be avoided wherever possible.

The attributes `range` and `unit` are not always required. Whether these two attributes are required depends on the *datatype* of the variable.

range Restriction on the permissible values of the variable. Mandatory if the datatype is the variable is one of `int`, `float`, or `enum`. The range is obsolete if the datatype is `bool`. Specifying the range is optional for `string` and `time`.

unit Physical unit of the measured value. Mandatory if the datatype is `int` or `float`. In all other cases, the *unit* has no meaning and must not be given. Units can either be defined by specifying an appropriate name, but it is strongly suggested to use controlled terms as described in Section 4.1

Listing 3.2 gives some examples of valid variables.

```
1 variable Temperature {
2     name: "Temperature"
3     description: "Measured temperature."
4     datatype: float
5     dimension: []
6     range: (-5, 40)
7     unit: CEL
8 }
9
10 variable Position {
11     name: "Position"
12     description: "3D position given in Euclidian coordinates."
13     datatype: int
14     dimension: [3]
15     range: (-10, 10)
16     unit: MTR
17 }
18
19 variable EmergencyStop {
20     name: "Emergency Stop"
21     description: "Specifies whether the emergency stop has
22     recently triggered and is currently active."
23     datatype: bool
24     dimension: []
25 }
```

Listing 3.2: Example of well-defined variables

Info: Attributes of measurements

According to the SOIL metamodel, a measurement has more attributes than described by the variable above, namely *value*, *uncertainty*, *label*, and *hash*. Whereas *value* and *uncertainty* are mandatory for each measurement, *label* and *hash* are optional. Those attributes are not part of the SOIL domain-specific language (DSL) because these attributes do not have meaningful static default values.

Info: Attributes of parameters

In contrast to measurements, the SOIL metamodel does not specify any more attributes for parameters than those attributes that are part of the SOIL DSL. However, the parameter's default *value* can be specified when the parameter is defined as child of a component (c.f. Section 3.4.1).

3.2.1 Datatypes

SOIL defines six "primitive" datatypes. For each variable, the datatype this variable has must be defined.

bool Boolean value, either true or false.

int : Integer values.

float : Floating point values.

string : A string of characters.

enum : If a variable has datatype *enum*, the range of this variable defines a fixed set of permissible values.

time : Time consists of date, time of day, and time zone information. The precision should be as high as possible (ideally up to milliseconds or nanoseconds). In the syntax of SOIL, a time value is specified according to RFC3339, which is defined here: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc3339>, e.g., 2022-03-27T10:44:30.526Z.

3.2.2 Dimension

The dimension is decoded as a list in the following way: To indicate a scalar, the empty list is used. Given a natural number greater than zero, the corresponding dimension has the given length. A zero indicates a dimension of unbounded size. Examples: [3,3] is a 3x3 matrix, [0] is a list of (theoretically) infinite length, and [5,3,0] is a three-dimensional matrix that has an infinite third dimension.

3.2.3 Range

The range restricts the number of permissible values of a variable.

boolean trivially restricted to `true` or `false`. Range specification must not be given.

int (*lower bound*, *upper bound*), to model an unconstrained value (top or bottom) don't set the corresponding entry (c.f. hint below)

float same as `int`

string (*lower bound, upper bound*), the bounds restrict the allowed length of the string, where the natural lower bound is zero, if not explicitly specified. Values smaller than zero are not allowed for *lower bound*. Values for *upper bound* must be greater than zero.

time same as int

enum Reference to the type definition of an *enum*. In a SOIL model specified like: range: State, where State is an *enum* previously defined.

Tip: Defining one limit only

It is possible to define none or only one limit (either min or max) of the interval. How this is done is shown below:

```
1 range: (,5) # All values smaller or equal to five are
    allowed.
2 range: (10,) # All values larger or equal to ten are
    allowed.
3 range: (,) # There is no restriction on the permissible
    values.
```

3.3 Functions

Function types have two optional attributes (additional to name and description of every *element type*): *arguments* and *returns*. The attribute must not be given if a function does not have arguments or returns, respectively. The expected arguments and yielded returns are specified by using previously defined *variable types*. The usage is given in the following form: <Type> name.

Some well-defined examples of function definitions are below, provided that well-formed *variable types* used below are defined (c.f. Listing 3.2).

```
1 function Jog {
2     name: "Jog"
3     description: "Jogs the head of a theodolite according to the
4     given angles."
5     arguments: Angle azimuth
6                 Angle elevation
7 }
8 function Reset {
9     name: "Reset"
10    description: "Resets the device to its initial state."
11    arguments: HardReset hard
12    returns: Success success
13 }
```

```

14
15 function findTarget {
16     name: "Find Target"
17     description: "Tries to find the target with a specified name
18     ."
19     arguments: Name target
20     returns: Success found
21             Position position
22 }

```

Listing 3.3: Example of well-defined functions

Tip: Order of arguments and returns

In contrast to well-known programming languages, the order of the *arguments* and *returns* of *functions* does not matter because we always pass the value of those together with the respective identifier.

To provide context-relevant information *name* and *description* attribute of *arguments* and *returns* can be *overridden*(c.f. Section 3.4.2).

When specifying the *arguments* and *returns* of *functions*, it is possible to use possibility **two** for overriding/defining default values as explained in Section 3.4.1

3.4 Components

Each *component* contains an arbitrary number of children elements, so the overall model has a tree-like shape. The definition of the children is done analogously to arguments and returns of functions. Two simple examples for *components* are:

```

1 component Target {
2     name: "Target"
3     description: "Entity of which the position can be measured."
4     parameters: Name name
5                 Calibration cal
6     measurements: Position position
7                 Orientation orientation
8 }
9
10 component Lasertracker {
11     name: "Lasertracker"
12     description: "Active coordinate measurement device based on
13     so-called laser interferometry for Large-Scale Metrology
14     applications."
15     parameters: Calibration cal
16     functions: ShutDown shutdown

```

```

15     components: BaseStations bases
16             MobileTarget mobiles
17 }

```

Listing 3.4: Example of well-defined components

Warning: Unique children names

The names of children must be unique, e.g., if there is a measurement `Position position` (as in the example above), there must not be another child who is named `position` (independent of the type of this child).

There are some more characteristics of components, which will be explained in detail below:

- How default values of parameters can be defined is described in Section 3.4.1
- Within a component type definition, one can *override* the name and description of its children, as described in Section 3.4.2
- How parameters can be defined to be *constant* is explained in Section 3.4.3
- SOIL allows *extending* components, which is described in Section 3.4.6
- It is possible, to define *dynamic* components. Dynamic components can be instantiated arbitrarily often during runtime, allowing modeling sensor systems to manage various equally working sensors (e.g., distributed environment monitoring systems). A more detailed explanation can be found in Section 3.4.5
- In addition to these basic attributes, it is possible to define *streams* for automatic and continuous data streaming (c.f. Section 5.2) and *events* to send predefined messages when values of variables meet a certain condition (c.f. Section 5.1).
- Measurements can be defined as *internal*, which helps define a semantic SOIL model. *Internal* measurements are explained in detail in Section 3.4.7.

3.4.1 Defining default values of *parameters*

SOIL offers three possibilities to define the default value of a parameter:

1. a) when defining the child parameters of a component in its `parameters` attribute
b) when defining the argument or return of a function in the respective attributes
2. when defining the child components of a component in its `components` attribute
3. in the *interface definition* described in Section 3.5

For the resulting sensor interface, the default values of parameters are determined in the following way:

- A default value defined by possibility **two**, overrides a default value defined by possibility **one**,
- a default value defined by possibility **three**, overrides a default value defined by possibility **two**,

How to make use of possibilities two and three is illustrated below.

```

1  variable Azimuth {
2      name: "Azimuth"
3      description: "An angle."
4      datatype: int
5      dimension: []
6      range: (0, 180)
7      unit: degree
8  }
9
10 component Trigger {
11     name: "Trigger"
12     description: "Trigger for measurements."
13     parameters: Azimuth azimuth = 25
14 }
15
16 component Sensor {
17     name: "Sensor"
18     description: "A simple sensor."
19     components: Trigger trigger(azimuth = 19)
20 }

```

Listing 3.5: Examples showing the override of default values of components

3.4.2 Overriding meta-information

In order to adapt the name and description of an element with context information, it is possible to set the name and description of an element when it is created as a child of a component or used as an argument or return in a function. The attributes can only be overridden in the component in which they are created. It is impossible to override the attributes of children defined in a base component.

An example is illustrated here:

```

1  variable Azimuth {
2      name: "Azimuth"
3      description: "An angle."
4      datatype: int
5      dimension: []
6      range: (0, 180)
7      unit: degree

```

```

8 }
9
10 component Trigger {
11     name: "Trigger"
12     description: "Trigger for measurements."
13     parameters: Azimuth azimuth = 25
14
15     azimuth.description = "The threshold for the azimuth angle
16     at which an event is triggered".
17 }
18 component Sensor {
19     name: "Sensor"
20     description: "A simple sensor."
21     components: Trigger trigger(azimuth = 19)
22
23     trigger.name = "Barrier trigger"
24     trigger.description = "Handles the publication of events,
25     dependent on the state of the barrier".
26 }

```

Listing 3.6: Examples of the override of meta-information

Tip: Arguments and Returns

It is also possible to override the `name` and `description` of arguments and returns within the definition of a function type.

3.4.3 Constant parameters

Parameters can be defined as `constant` by using the respective keyword, as can be seen in the example below. It does not have any consequence for the development process of the SOIL model, but a parameter defined as `constant` can not be changed during runtime. More precisely, in the generation step for constant parameters, the setter (and in the case of HTTP protocol, no PATCH endpoint) will not be generated. Note that a parameter defined as `constant` must define a default value on the component level, i.e., according to possibility **one** described above. The value can be overridden as described above.

```

1 variable MACAddress {
2     name: "MAC Address"
3     description: "The MAC address of the device."
4     datatype: string
5     dimension: []
6 }
7
8 component Sensor {

```

```

9     name: "Sensor"
10    description: "A simple sensor."
11    parameters:
12        constant MACAddress mac = "AB:CD:EF:98:76:54"
13 }

```

Listing 3.7: Examples of constant parameters

3.4.4 Streaming functions

Functions can have *streaming* behavior, which is particularly useful for complex measurement routines where the same outputs are measured multiple times. A streaming function transmits its outputs via a publish/subscribe protocol, i.e. usually split up into multiple consecutive messages. In contrast to that, a function without this modifier, provides the outputs, ones as the direct response to the request triggering the function.

A function is marked as *streaming* by using the keyword `streaming`, when defining a child component:

```

1 component Lasertracker {
2     name: "Lasertracker"
3     description: "Active coordinate measurement device based on
4     \"so-called \" laser interferometry for Large-Scale Metrology
5     applications."
6     functions: streaming Measure measure
7 }

```

Listing 3.8: Examples of a dynamic child component

3.4.5 Dynamic components

Without *dynamic components* a SOIL interface is entirely static. All elements are initiated exactly once for an interface. However, existing measuring devices, such as laser trackers, can have an arbitrary number of targets, which can be added during operation. This must be reflected in the interface. So, *dynamic components* serve the purpose of being dynamically added or removed at runtime.

A component is marked as *dynamic* by using the keyword `dynamic`, when defining a child component:

```

1 component Lasertracker {
2     name: "Lasertracker"
3     description: "Active coordinate measurement device based on
4     \"so-called \" laser interferometry for Large-Scale Metrology
5     applications."
6     components: dynamic MobileTarget mobiles
7 }

```

Listing 3.9: Examples of a dynamic child component

3.4.6 Extending components

For components, SOIL implements an *inheritance* relation, which allows to *extend* a defined component with additional children by using the keyword `extends` and specifying a base component. When extending a component, the subcomponent is composed of all the children its base component is composed of. The basic attributes *name* and *description* must be set also for the subcomponent. Consider the following example:

```
1 component BaseEntity {
2     name: "Base Entity"
3     description: "A simple Base Station."
4     parameters: Elevation elev
5                 Position pos
6     functions: Reset reset
7 }
8
9 component ExtendedBaseEntity extends BaseEntity {
10     name: "Extended Base Entity"
11     description: "More fancy base station with more attributes."
12     measurements: Distance dist1, dist2, dist3
13                  BatteryLevel bat
14     functions: Jog jog
15 }
```

Listing 3.10: Examples of the extension mechanism for components

Info: Number of children

In this case, *ExtendedBaseEntity* has eight children in total. Two parameters, four measurements, and two functions.

Warning: Unique children names

Changing the type of children in a subcomponent is impossible, i.e., children's names must be unique across the inheritance chain. For example, if the base component has a parameter `Position pos`, the subcomponent (or subcomponents of those) must not define a child with the name `pos`.

3.4.7 Internal measurements

Using the keyword `internal` indicates the child measurement is of a value that is also a property of the device itself. This has no implication for the technical implementation of the interface but allows for a more fine-grained semantic description and increases the interoperability of the data model. For example, for a wireless sensor node, this could be the measurement of the battery level or signal strength, see Listing 7.1.

3.5 Interfaces

Interfaces are parts of SOIL models that define the root component of that SOIL interface. For that, the keyword `interface` is followed by the "name" of a properly defined component. Moreover, an *interface* allows for setting (or overriding) the default value for all parameters the interface contains, i.e., the values of all parameters that are children of components of the model. For example:

```
1 interface Lasertracker lasertracker {
2     cal = " "
3     bases.base1.pos      = (5.3, 5.1, 8.2)
4     bases.base2.pos      = (2.3, 3.0, 7.2)
5     bases.base3.pos      = (5.3, 5.1, 8.2)
6     mobiles.mobile2.pos  = (0.0, 0.0, 0.0)
7 }
```

Listing 3.11: Examples of an interface

Info: Explanation of Listing 3.11

The above example is a valid *initialization* of an *interface* if the component `Lasertracker` has a parameter called "cal" of datatype `string`, a child component with "name" `bases`, which itself has a child component with "name" `base1` having a child parameter with "name" `pos` (having a dimension, datatype and range the value specified here conform to), and so on...

Tip: Omitting default values in the interface

It is not required to set the values for all interface parameters.

Caution: Only one interface per file

The *interface* can be considered as the "SOIL-counterpart" to the main function of well-known programming languages. Thus, defining multiple *interfaces* in a single file is not allowed. During generation *interfaces* defined in imported files (c.f. Section 5.4) are ignored. Although, in general, it would be possible to allow multiple definitions and generate the interface implementation for multiple *interfaces* in one file at once, it is not supported to reduce the overall complexity.

Warning: Omitting an interface definition

The files will be parsed and validated if no interface is defined, but no model or implementation will be generated.

Using controlled terms

One of the key features of SOIL is the abstraction of semantic features, i.e., the possibility to create FAIR sensor data models based on semantic web standards without needing extensive knowledge of semantic modeling. SOIL deals with that by providing dedicated mechanisms for using controlled terms from available terminologies, vocabularies, and ontologies. SOIL differentiates between two different cases for using controlled terms. First, controlled terms can be used to define the unit of *variables*. Second, a controlled term can be specified for each *element*, specifying the concept to be modeled by this particular *element*. The usage of such a controlled term is always indicated using angle brackets, i.e., the smaller and larger sign, as shown in Listing 4.2

To use a controlled term, its namespace must be defined first. Utilizing the syntax of Turtle, namespaces are defined at the begin of a file using the keyword `@prefix`, and specifying the prefix of and the reference (using persistent URL) to the namespace, as depicted in Listing 4.1.

```
1 @prefix quantitykind: <http://qudt.org/vocab/quantitykind/> ;
2 @prefix unit: <http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/> ;
3 @prefix dbo: <http://dbpedia.org/ontology/> ;
4 @prefix schema: <http://schema.org/> ;
```

Listing 4.1: Example of definition prefixes

4.1 Units

Controlled terms can be used instead of defining the unit by a simple string, as shown in line 12 of Listing 4.2.

```
1 @prefix unit: <http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/> ;
2 @prefix quantitykind: <http://qudt.org/vocab/quantitykind/> ;
3
4 variable TCP defines <quantitykind:CartesianCoordinates> {
5     name: "Tool Center Point"
6     description: "Tool center point of a six-joint robot."
7     datatype: float
8     range: (-0.5,0.5)
9     dimension: [3]
10    unit: <unit:M>
11 }
```

Listing 4.2: Example of a unit definition using controlled terms.

Tip: Preferred Ontology for units

The preferred ontology for units is QUDT, as it provides an extensive list of well-described and documented physical units.

4.2 Targeting controlled terms

SOIL can be used to specify the definition of concepts described by a controlled term. The exact realisation of the definition depends on the exact *Element*. In the case of *Measurements*, the controlled term *defined* using the keyword `defines` is translated into the physical quantity of that *Measurement* (i.e., the property `qudt:hasQuantityKind`). In the case of *Parameters* and *Components*, the defined controlled term is translated to the `rdf:type` of that *Parameter* or *Component*, respectively.

An example of such a definition is depicted in line 4 of Listing 4.2.

Tip: Defining Variables

I strongly suggest always *define* physical quantities for *variable*, as shown in Listing 4.2. If the modeled *variable* is no (physical) quantity, I strongly suggest omitting the `defines` keyword.

Advanced features

Based on the basic building blocks described above, this chapter introduces additional features that enable automatically configured continuous data streaming.

5.1 Events

Events are used to notify the user about notable changes of measurement or parameter values, which might require manual action. On an abstract level, an *event* in the context of SOIL consists of the following parts:

- An **element**, i.e. a *measurement* or *parameter* the event is applied to.
- A **target** is a specified value compared to the actual value of the *element*.
- A **trigger**, i.e. a logical or numerical comparison operator (such as *equal*, *less*, *greater* and *not* or a logically valid combination of those). The event is called *triggered* if and only if the comparison of the actual value of the *element* with the *target* using the defined *trigger* is evaluated to `true`. Example: the actual value of the measurement *temperature* is `37.5`, the defined *target* is `35` and the *trigger* is *equal or greater* (i.e. `>=`). Evaluating the term `37.5 >= 35` yields `true`, which means the event is considered as *triggered*.
- A **severity** that specifies how critical it is if the event is *triggered*. We define five levels of *severity*:
 - **debug**: Lowest level. Should only be given to events used to monitor the behavior during development.
 - **info**: Used to give the user feedback that something has changed, but this change has no major implication to the device's functioning.
 - **warning**: Something has happened that should grab the operators' attention, but an intervention of the operator is not necessarily required.
 - **error**: Something is not working correctly. The intervention of the operator is required.
 - **critical**: Something happened that imposes a danger to the device and might cause the device to stop working. The intervention of the operator is required as soon as possible.
- A **message** containing a descriptive explanation of the event published whenever the event is *triggered*.

Info: Only one-dimensional variables can have events

An unambiguous definition of the trigger-target combination for multidimensional measurements or parameters is not trivial. Furthermore, the triggers `smaller` and `greater` are not applicable for measurements or parameters with datatype `string`, `bool`, or `enum`. Whereas the latter is easy to check, the first issue is more complex to solve. To overcome this issue, we restrict the definition of events to one-dimensional values for now.

The general syntax of an *event* looks like this:

```
1 if <name of the measurement or parameter> <trigger> <target>: <
  severity>(<message>)
```

Listing 5.1: Informal definition of the syntax of events

Here is a small example illustrating the definition of events:

```
1 component Entity {
2   name: "Entity"
3   description: "A mobile Entity, same functions as BaseEntity
  but is mobile and runs on a battery"
4   measurements: BatteryLevel bat
5   parameters: Interval interval
6
7   if bat <= 15: warning("Battery level low")
8   if interval < 60: info("Very short interval")
9 }
```

Listing 5.2: Example of events

Info: Only one-dimensional variables can have events

Note, from *severity*, no implicit program flow is deduced, i.e., there are no exceptions or errors generated for events with *severity error* or *critical*. The severity is only used to set a value for the key "severity" of a published message.

5.2 Streams

SOIL provides mechanisms to pre-configure the streaming behaviour of a *FAIR sensor service*. It can be specified if certain values can be constantly published using dedicated protocols (such as MQTT, UDP, etc.).

5.2.1 Streaming measurements

Components can define *streams* to automatically publish the values of measurement children, according to settings defined in a *stream*. Generally, we distinguish three possibilities for how to configure the (continuous) streaming of measurement values:

fixed Publishment of the current value at fixed, statically defined time intervals. This means the developer specifies this time interval in seconds when developing the interface.

dynamic Publishment of the current value at dynamically defined time intervals. For that, the measurement in question must have sibling parameter of with datatype `int` or `float`. The value of this parameter is then used as a time interval for the publishment. The unit of interval (e.g., seconds or minutes, is given by the *unit* of the parameter).

update On-demand publishing of fresh measurement values. This means it is published whenever a new measurement value is produced (which also can lead to irregular intervals).

The syntax of streams is straight-forward and illustrated in the example below:

```
1     component Entity {
2         name: "Entity"
3         description: "A mobile Entity, same functions as
4         BaseEntity but is mobile and runs on a battery"
5         measurements: BatteryLevel bat
6                     Position pos
7                     SignalStrength signal
8         parameters: Interval interval
9
10        streams:
11            bat: fixed(10)
12            pos: dynamic(interval)
13            signal: update
14    }
```

Listing 5.3: Example of streams

5.2.2 Streaming from functions

Using the keyword `streaming` in the header of the definition of a *Function* (see Section 3.3). By that, the results returned by the function are not sent back as a response to the request calling the function but are published using the dedicated protocol. Multiple and continuous responses for a function are possible using streaming functions, e.g., starting a measurement routine to produce a certain amount of dedicated measurements.

Info: Streaming functions in Python

When generating the Python implementation from a SOIL model, a streaming function is translated into a generator function instead of a standard method, i.e., the results are returned using `yield` instead of `return`.

5.3 List of variables

To reduce redundancy Variables (i.e. Parameters, Measurements, Arguments, and Returns) can also be instantiated as "Lists" of the variable type (cf. Listing 5.4). The keyword `List` effectively prepends an additional dimension of arbitrary length to the dimension of the instantiated variable type, e.g. the dimension `[3]`, becomes `[0,3]`. This is particularly useful for functions returning an arbitrary number of measurements of the same type.

```
1     component BaseEntity {
2         description: "A simple Base Station."
3         parameters: Elevation elevation
4                     List Position pos
5         functions:  Reset reset
6     }
```

Listing 5.4: Example of a variable list.

Warning: Sparsely tested feature

This feature has not yet been fully tested. So, bugs cannot be ruled out.

5.4 Imports

It is possible to import other SOIL files. Imports are always absolute (in a way) or, even more precisely, relative to the SOIL file containing the interface. Imports are a simplified version of Python imports. The file name imports the files specified in the `import` statements. The fully qualified name has to be used to use element definitions from an imported file. The examples in Listing 5.5 and Listing 5.6 below illustrate the usage.

```
1     component BaseEntity {
2         description: "A simple Base Station."
3         parameters: Elevation elevation
4                     Position pos
5         functions:  Reset reset
6     }
```

Listing 5.5: Example for importing SOIL files - Part 1: File *base.soil*

```
1 import base
2
3 component ExtendedBaseEntity extends base.BaseEntity {
4     description: "Advanced BaseStation"
5     measurements: Distance dist1, dist2, dist3
6                 BatteryLevel bat
7     functions:   Jog jog
8 }
```

Listing 5.6: Example for importing SOIL files - Part 2: File *exteions.soil* which is located in the same directory as the file *base.soil*

Caution: Limitations for imports

Although theoretically possible to implement, SOIL does not allow importing files that are not in the same directory as the "main" file defining the interface to be generated. This restriction has been made to reduce the complexity of defined interfaces. Moreover, it simplifies software development for parsing and validating SOIL models and generating SOIL interfaces.

Part II

The Python Unified Device Interface

The Python Unified Device Interface

The Python Unified Device Interface (PUDI) is a framework to produce FAIR Sensor Data providing an HTTP and MQTT interface to transmit the data to clients. The library should only be used with template software generated from a SOIL model using the SOIL-Editor.

The implementation of a measuring device using SOIL is described in section 6.1.

A detailed, technical description of the interplay of REST endpoints and the generated Python source codes is given in section 6.2. However, this section is only for information and those who want to dive deeply into the logic of PUDI.

6.1 Implementation of a CPMS using SOIL in Python

Given a SOIL model defined as described in Part I, one can generate a template for implementing the

- every component is translated into a Python class, further denoted as *component class*
- every function is translated into a method of a class
- every measurement of a component is translated into an attribute of a Python class and getter to this attribute
- every parameter of a component is translated into an attribute of a Python class and a getter to this attribute. If the parameter is not marked as "constant" a setter is generated.

To implement the logic of the measuring device the following approach should be followed:

1. Definition of the SOIL model using the SOIL manual
2. Generation of the Python implementation
3. Creation of the HWC exploiting the *TOP mechanism* explained below in subsection 6.1.1
4. Re-generation of the Python implementation using the SOIL model of step 1 and the HWC of step 3

6.1.1 The TOP-Mechanism

To avoid HWC being overwritten (and thus deleted) when re-generating the implementation (e.g., due to updates to the underlying SOIL model), the implementation should be done in a sub-class derived from the generated classes. For that, the base class must be implemented in a separate file, as shown in Listing 6.1 and Listing 6.2.

```
1 class GeneratedClass(object):
2     def __init__():
3         pass
```

Listing 6.1: Generated Python class extended by the HWC-class in Listing 6.2 to implement its logic.

```
1 import gen_class.GeneratedClass
2
3 class HandwrittenClass(GeneratedClass):
4     def __init__():
5         GeneratedClass.__init__()
```

Listing 6.2: HWC Python class implementing the logic of the extended, generated class in Listing 6.1.

However, in tree-like class structures, such as those generated from SOIL models, this results in multiple problems and challenges, as described by Rumpe et al. (p. 110f). Therefore, SOIL implements the TOP mechanism described by Rumpe et al.. Instead of defining and declaring a custom sub-class a class is created in a separate file having the **exact same** file name and class name as the generated class. By passing this file as HWC to an additional generation step, the generation process will analyze all provided HWC and generate for every already existing class a super-class by pending "TOP" to the generated class name, as shown below in Listing 6.3 and Listing 6.4.

```
1 class GeneratedClassTOP(object):
2     def __init__():
3         pass
```

Listing 6.3: Generated Python class extended by the HWC-class in Listing 6.4 to implement its logic.

```
1 import gen_class.GeneratedClassTOP
2
3 class GeneratedClass(GeneratedClassTOP):
4     def __init__():
5         GeneratedClassTOP.__init__()
```

Listing 6.4: HWC Python class implementing the logic of the extended, generated class in Listing 6.3.

Following the *TOP mechanism* simplifies the implementation of a measuring device using SOIL, especially if not the implementation of all of the generated *component classes* must be manually adapted.

6.1.2 Implementation suggestions

For the implementation of the logic of the measurement device, an empty class `Device` is generated, which does not have any attributes or methods by default. Exactly one object of the class `Device` must be generated first before the *root component class* of the model is instantiated. This `device` object is passed to every *component class* of the model so that the implementation and values of the internal sensor logic are accessible everywhere in the framework.

The generated source code can be started by using the following `main.py` file, where all occurrences of "root component" must be replaced by the module or class of the root component of the SOIL model, respectively. The snippet shown in Listing 6.5 ensures, everything is properly setup.

```
1 import toml
2
3 import start
4 from hwc.device import Device
5 from hwc.com_rootcomponent import COMRootComponent
6
7 if __name__ == '__main__':
8     device = Device()
9     root_component = COMRootComponent(device)
10
11     start.start(root_component, toml.load('config.toml'), 'model
    .json')
```

Listing 6.5: Exemplary content of the file `main.py` for starting the CPMS based on the generated source code.

It is strongly suggested to implement all sensor logic in the `Device` class or introduce additional classes for that, which are then used within the `Device` class. The generated *component classes* should only be used as wrapper to read (or write) attributes of the `Device` object. An example for such a properly generated getter of measurement is shown in Listing 6.6.

```
1 from com_lasertracker import COMLasertrackerTOP
2
3 class COMLasertracker(COMLasertrackerTOP):
4
5     def __init__(self, device: Device, manufacturer: str = ""):
6         COMLasertrackerTOP.__init__(self, device, manufacturer)
7
8     def get_par_state(self):
9         return str(self._device.state)
```

Listing 6.6: Example of wrapping the logic of the CPMS implemented in the `Device` class.

Only very simple parameters which do not influence the logic of the measuring device should be solely handled outside the `Device` class in the *component classes*. An example for that would be a parameter "manufacturer" (see Listing 6.7). All other attributes should be removed in the generated *component classes* and moved to the `Device` class as described above.

```
1 from com_lasertracker import COMLasertrackerTOP
2
3 class COMLasertrackerTOP(object):
4
5     def __init__(self, device: Device, manufacturer: str = ""):
6         self._device = device
7         self._par_manufacturer = manufacturer
8
9     def get_par_manufacturer(self) -> str:
10        return self._par_manufacturer
```

Listing 6.7: Example of a parameter of the CPMS which does not affect the devices logic, and can therefore be handled directly (and not in the `Device` class).

6.2 Details on the programm flow of the CPMS implemented with PUDI

The major difference between PUDI as implemented and provided by the python package `wz1-udi` compared to the most other common packages is the inversed control of the programm flow. Most packages are common *libraries* offering modules and functions which are imported or called within the implemented software. The control of the programm flow and its main logic however is implemented by the developer of the software using of the library. In contrast to that, PUDI is a *framework* which inverts this behaviour. This means, the programm flow and main logic is controlled and implemented by the framework, calling methods implemented by the developer using the framework.¹

However, this increases the perceived complexity of the developed source code and software, as the programm flow hard to understand, as it is hidden in the framework. This section explains the programm flow using PUDI and, therefore, hopefully simplifies the usage of SOIL and PUDI.

The thing most hard to understand is probably:

"How does the variable in my implementation storing the value of a measurement (or parameter) is automatically sent via MQTT or accesible via the REST-API?"

For explaining how this works, lets consider the very simple SOIL model in Listing 6.8, the generated *component class* of the *component type* `TemperatureSensor` in Listing 6.9, and the generated serialization of the SOIL model as JSON in Listing 6.10.

¹A more detailed explanation on the difference between software *libraries* and *frameworks* can be found here.

```

1 @prefix quantitykind: <http://qudt.org/vocab/quantitykind/> ;
2 @prefix unit: <http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/> ;
3
4 variable Temperature defines <quantitykind:Temperature> {
5     name: "Temperature"
6     description: "Measured temperature."
7     datatype: float
8     dimension: []
9     range: (-5, 40)
10    unit: <unit:DEG_C>
11 }
12
13 component TemperatureSensor {
14     name: "Temperature sensor"
15     description: "Sensor measuring a temperature."
16     measurements:
17         Temperature temperature
18
19     streams:
20         temperature: fixed(10)
21 }
22
23 interface TemperatureSensor sensor {}

```

Listing 6.8: Very simple SOIL model having one variable and one component using this variable as measurement. Moreover, the component defines a fixed stream for this measurement.

```

1 from typing import List
2 from typing import Tuple
3 from typing import Any
4 from wzl.soil.stream import Job, FixedJob, ConfigurableJob,
    UpdateJob, EventJob
5 from wzl.soil.event import Event, EventTrigger, EventSeverity
6 from device import Device
7
8 class COMTemperatureSensor(object):
9
10    def __init__(self, device: Device):
11        self._device = device
12        self._mea_temperature = 0
13
14    def get_mea_temperature(self) -> Tuple[float, Any]:
15        return self._mea_temperature, None
16
17    def streams(self, fqid: str) -> List[Job]:
18        schedule = []

```

```

19         schedule += [FixedJob(f"{fqid}/MEA-Temperature", 10,
self.get_mea_temperature)]
20         return schedule

```

Listing 6.9: The component class of the temperature sensor generated from the model in Listing 6.8.

```

1  {
2      "uuid": "COM-Sensor",
3      "name": "Temperature sensor",
4      "description": "Sensor measuring a temperature.",
5      "profile": "TemperatureSensor",
6      "measurements": [
7          {
8              "uuid": "MEA-Temperature",
9              "name": "Temperature",
10             "description": "Measured temperature.",
11             "profile": "TemperatureSensorTemperature",
12             "datatype": "float",
13             "unit": "unit:DEG_C",
14             "dimension": [],
15             "range": [ -5, 40 ],
16             "value": 0
17         }
18     ],
19     "parameters": [],
20     "functions": [],
21     "components": []
22 }

```

Listing 6.10: The JSON serialization of the SOIL model of the temperature sensor as defined in Listing 6.8.

Executing the source code, the served HTTP REST-API offers to endpoints:

- an endpoint for the sensor component reachable at the location "COM-Sensor/"
- an endpoint for the temperature measurement reachable at the location "COM-Sensor/MEA-Temperature"

If the endpoint of the measurement (i.e., "COM-Sensor/MEA-Temperature") is requested via HTTP-GET PUDI resolves the location and, then,

1. serializes the meta-information to JSON, stored by PUDI based on the deserialization of the JSON representation in Listing 6.10 at start-up,
2. and calls the getter function for that measurement, i.e., the function defined in lines 14-15 of Listing 6.8.

The value and uncertainty returned by this function call are then included in the serialized JSON representation and returned via PUDI as a response to the HTTP-GET request.

Analogously, the definition of the fixed stream for this measurement in line 20 of the SOIL model in Listing 6.8 configures PUDI to call the getter method of this measurement every 10 seconds. The returned value and uncertainty are then published together with all meta information of the measurement via MQTT under the topic "<root-topic>/COM-Sensor/MEA-Temperature".

Part III

Annex

This chapter contains examples of fictional (measuring) systems.

The implementation of all examples can be found at the public GitLab group of the author's chair: <https://git-ce.rwth-aachen.de/wzl-mq-public/soil/soil-dummies>.

7.1 Virtual Environmental Monitoring System

Listing 7.1 gives an example of a fictional environmental sensor system. The interface defines a root component that manages an arbitrary number of sensors. The example illustrates the usage of dynamic components, streams and events.

```
1 @prefix quantitykind: <http://qudt.org/vocab/quantitykind/> ;
2 @prefix unit: <http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/> ;
3
4 variable Location {
5     name: "Location"
6     description: "Human interpretable description of the current location of
7     the sensor."
8     datatype: string
9     dimension: []
10 }
11 variable BatteryLevel {
12     name: "Battery level"
13     description: "Battery level"
14     datatype: int
15     range: (0, 100)
16     dimension: []
17     unit: <unit:PERCENT>
18 }
19
20 variable SignalStrength defines <quantityKind:SignalStrength> {
21     name: "Signal strength"
22     description: "Strength of the signal of the wireless environmental sensor
23     ."
24     datatype: int
25     range: (0, 100)
26     dimension: []
27     unit: <unit:PERCENT>
28 }
29 variable Temperature defines <quantityKind:Temperature> {
30     name: "Ambient temperature"
31     description: "The current ambient temperature."
32     datatype: float
33     range: (-20, 50)
34     dimension: []
35     unit: <unit:DEG_C>
```

```

36 }
37
38 variable Pressure defines <quantityKind:AtmosphericPressure> {
39     name: "Relative air pressure"
40     description: "The current air pressure."
41     datatype: float
42     range: (900, 1200)
43     dimension: []
44     unit: <unit:HectoPA>
45 }
46
47 variable Humidity defines <quantityKind:RelativeHumidity> {
48     name: "Relative humidity"
49     description: "Relative humidity."
50     datatype: float
51     range: (0, 100)
52     dimension: []
53     unit: <unit:PERCENT>
54 }
55
56 component EnvironmentalSensor {
57     name: "Environmental Sensor"
58     description: "A single wireless environmental sensor, measuring
59     temperature, pressure and humidity."
60     measurements:
61         Temperature temperature
62         Pressure pressure
63         Humidity humidity
64         internal SignalStrength signalStrength
65         internal BatteryLevel batteryLevel
66     parameters:
67         Location location
68
69     streams:
70         temperature: fixed(30)
71         pressure: fixed(30)
72         humidity: fixed(30)
73         signalStrength: fixed(60)
74         batteryLevel: fixed(60)
75
76     if batteryLevel < 5: warning("Battery level is low, please replace
77     battery. Otherwise the sensor will not send data anymore.")
78 }
79
80 component EnvironmentalSensorManager {
81     name: "Manager of environmental sensors"
82     description: "Manages a set of environmental sensors"
83     components:
84         dynamic EnvironmentalSensor sensor(location="Pillar A")
85 }
86
87 interface EnvironmentalSensorManager sensorManager {}

```

Listing 7.1: Full example of a fictional virtual environmental sensor system

7.2 Virtual Laser Tracker

The example of a virtual laser tracker demonstrates the usage of imports and (re-)use of defined elements in different components. The example consists of multiple listings, each with a single SOIL file. Moreover, the example shows the override of default values and meta-information and the usage of dynamic components.

```
1 @prefix schema: <http://schema.org/> ;
2 @prefix unit: <http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/> ;
3
4 import utils;
5 import base_stations;
6 import mobile_entities;
7
8 variable Time defines <schema:DateTime> {
9     name: "Time"
10    description: "Current system time."
11    datatype: time
12    dimension: []
13 }
14
15 variable Version defines <schema:version> {
16     name: "Version"
17     description: "Incremental API-Version."
18     datatype: int
19     range: (0, 100)
20     dimension: []
21     unit: <unit:UNITLESS>
22 }
23
24 variable Manufacturer defines <schema:manufacturer> {
25     name: "Manufacturer"
26     description: "Name of the manufacturing company."
27     datatype: string
28     dimension: []
29 }
30
31 function Reset {
32     name: "Reset"
33     description: "Resets the device into the same state like directly after
34     start-up."
35 }
36
37 function Shutdown {
38     name: "Shutdown"
39     description: "Gracefully shutdown the device."
40 }
41
42 component Lasertracker {
43     name: "Lasertracker"
44     description: "Active coordinate measurement device based on laser
45     interferometry for Large-Scale metrology applications."
46     components:
47         base_stations.BaseStations baseStations
48         mobile_entities.MobileEntities mobileEntities
```

```

47     functions:
48         Reset reset
49         Shutdown shutdown
50     parameters:
51         utils.State state = OK
52         constant Manufacturer manufacturer = "API"
53         constant Version version = 1
54         Time time
55
56     if state == ERROR: error("An error occurred!")
57 }
58
59 interface Lasertracker APIRadian {}

```

Listing 7.2: "Main" SOIL model file "lasertracker.soil" containing the interface definition.

```

1  @prefix quantitykind: <http://qudt.org/vocab/quantitykind/> ;
2  @prefix unit: <http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/> ;
3
4  import utils;
5
6  variable Azimuth defines <quantitykind:Angle> {
7      name: "Azimuth"
8      description: "Current position of azimuth rotation encoder in Radian."
9      datatype: float
10     dimension: []
11     unit: <unit:RAD>
12     range: (0, 3.14)
13 }
14
15 variable Elevation defines <quantitykind:Angle> {
16     name: "Elevation"
17     description: "Current position of elevation rotation encoder in Radian."
18     datatype: float
19     dimension: []
20     unit: <unit:RAD>
21     range: (0, 3.14)
22 }
23
24 variable Distance defines <quantitykind:Distance> {
25     name: "Distance"
26     description: "Measured distance to the currently activate target."
27     datatype: float
28     dimension: []
29     unit: <unit:M>
30     range: (0, 100)
31 }
32
33 variable Interval defines <quantitykind:Time> {
34     name: "Interval"
35     description: "Interval in seconds."
36     datatype: float
37     dimension: []
38     unit: <unit:SEC>
39     range: (0, 360)
40 }
41

```

```

42 function Jog {
43     name: "Jog"
44     description: "Jogs the tracker's head by the given angles for the azimuth
45         and elevation."
46     arguments:
47         Azimuth azimuth
48         Elevation elevation
49 }
50 function PointTo {
51     name: "Point to"
52     description: "Moves the tracker head so that the laser points to the
53         specified position."
54     arguments:
55         utils.Position position
56 }
57 component Base {
58     name: "Base"
59     description: "Represents a base station in a distributed system."
60     functions:
61         Jog jog
62         PointTo point_to
63     parameters:
64         utils.State state = OK
65         Interval interval = 10
66     measurements:
67         internal utils.Position position
68         internal utils.Quaternion quaternion
69         internal Azimuth azimuth
70         internal Elevation elevation
71         internal Distance distance
72
73     streams:
74         position: update
75         quaternion: update
76
77     if state == ERROR: error("An error of the trackers base occurred.")
78     if distance > 50.0: warning("Distance is very high. Measurements have
79         high uncertainty.")
80
81     position.description = "Position of the base of the tracker within a
82         global reference frame."
83     quaternion.description = "Orientation of the base in relation to the
84         orientation of a global reference frame."
85 }
86 component BaseStations {
87     name: "Base Stations"
88     description: "Object acting as a list of base stations of the metrology
89         system."
90     components:
91         Base base
92 }

```

Listing 7.3: SOIL model file "base_stations.soil" which defines the base station of a laser tracker.

```

1  @prefix unit: <http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/> ;
2
3  import utils;
4
5  enum Mode {
6      CONTINUOUS
7      TRIGGERED
8      EXTERNAL
9      IDLE
10 }
11
12 variable Mode {
13     name: "Mode"
14     description: "Current state of the entity. In CONTINUOUS mode, values are
15         dispatched as fast as possible. In TRIGGERED mode, values are only
16         dispatched after a software trigger. In EXTERNAL mode, values are
17         dispatched by an external trigger, e.g. probe or TTL. IDLE means the
18         entity is currently not used."
19     datatype: enum
20     range: Mode
21     dimension: []
22 }
23
24 variable Type {
25     name: "Type"
26     description: "System-specific identifier of the target Type, e.g. SMR or
27         Active SMR."
28     datatype: string
29     dimension: []
30 }
31
32 measurement Locked {
33     name: "Locked"
34     description: "Boolean flag specifying whether the target is locked in."
35     datatype: boolean
36     dimension: []
37 }
38
39 function Reset {
40     name: "Reset"
41     description: "Starts the search routine around the current direction."
42 }
43
44 variable Counter {
45     name: "Counter"
46     description: "Natural numeric value."
47     datatype: int
48     dimension: []
49     range: (1,1000)
50     unit: <unit:UNITLESS>
51 }
52
53 variable Label {
54     name: "Label"
55     description: "A string serving as comment."
56     datatype: string

```

```

52     dimension: []
53 }
54
55 function Trigger {
56     name: "Trigger"
57     description: "Trigger count measurements and set the resulting label.
58     This function is only allowed in triggered acquisition mode."
59     arguments:
60         Counter counter = 100
61         Label label
62     returns:
63         Position position
64         Label outputLabel
65 }
66
67 component Target {
68     name: "Target"
69     description: "Represents an individual mobile entity."
70     functions:
71         Reset reset
72         streaming Trigger trigger
73     measurements:
74         utils.Position position
75         utils.Quaternion quaternion
76         internal Locked locked
77     parameters:
78         utils.State state = OK
79         Mode mode = CONTINUOUS
80         Type type = "SMR"
81
82     streams:
83         position: update
84         quaternion: update
85
86     state.description = "Reflects the current state of the target. If logged
87     in: OK. If not stable: WARNING. If lost: ERROR."
88 }
89
90 component MobileEntities {
91     name: "Mobile Entities"
92     description: "Object acting as a list of mobile entities in the metrology
93     system."
94     components:
95         dynamic Target target
96 }

```

Listing 7.4: SOIL model file "mobile_entities.soil" which defines the mobile entities i.e. the targets of a laser tracker.

```

1 @prefix dbo: <http://dbpedia.org/ontology/> ;
2 @prefix quantitykind: <http://qudt.org/vocab/quantitykind/> ;
3 @prefix unit: <http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/> ;
4
5 enum State {
6     OK
7     WARNING
8     ERROR

```

```

9      MAINTENANCE
10 }
11
12 variable State defines <dbo:status> {
13     name: "State"
14     description: "The current state of the device."
15     datatype: enum
16     range: State
17     dimension: []
18 }
19
20 variable Position defines <quantitykind:CartesianCoordinates> {
21     name: "Position"
22     description: "Most recently dispatched measured position."
23     datatype: float
24     dimension: [3]
25     range: (-40, 40)
26     unit: <unit:M>
27 }
28
29 variable Quaternion defines <quantitykind:Angle> {
30     name: "Quaternion"
31     description: "Most recently dispatched measured orientation as a
32     quaternion, if available."
33     datatype: float
34     dimension: [4]
35     range: (0, 1)
36     unit: <unit:UNITLESS>
37 }

```

Listing 7.5: SOIL model file "utils.soil" contains utility elements used multiple other files of the example.

7.3 Fictional Mobile Robot

Listing 7.6 gives an example of a fictional mobile robot that can move freely. The example illustrates the extension mechanism for components.

```

1 variable Position {
2     name: "Position"
3     description: "Position in Cartesian coordinates given in meter."
4     datatype: float
5     range: (-50, 50)
6     dimension: [3]
7     unit: Metre
8 }
9
10 variable TCP {
11     name: "Tool Center Point"
12     description: "Tool center point of a six-arm robot."
13     datatype: float
14     range: (-0.5,0.5)
15     dimension: [3]
16     unit: Metre
17 }

```

```

18
19 variable BatteryLevel {
20     name: "Battery level"
21     description: "Battery level"
22     datatype: int
23     range: (0, 100)
24     dimension: []
25     unit: Percent
26 }
27
28 variable Open {
29     name: "Open"
30     description: "Flag to specify if something is open."
31     datatype: boolean
32     dimension: []
33 }
34
35 variable AutoMovement {
36     name: "Autonomous Movement"
37     description: "If true, the robot moves around freely and autonomously."
38     datatype: boolean
39     dimension: []
40 }
41
42 component Gripper {
43     name: "Gripper"
44     description: "Gripper of a robot"
45     parameters:
46         Open open = true
47 }
48
49 function GoTo {
50     name: "GoTo"
51     description: "Moves something to an absolute given position"
52     arguments:
53         Position position
54 }
55
56 function Step {
57     name: "Step"
58     description: "Moves something relatively from the current position to the
59         given position"
60     arguments:
61         Position position
62 }
63
64 component Robot {
65     name: "Robot"
66     description: "A robot arm with six axes."
67     measurements:
68         TCP tcp
69     components:
70         Gripper gripper
71     functions:
72         GoTo goto
73         Step step

```

```

73
74     streams:
75         tcp: fixed(10)
76 }
77
78 component MobileRobot extends Robot {
79     name: "Mobile Robot"
80     description: "A robot arm with six axes mounted on a movable platform."
81     measurements:
82         Position position
83         BatteryLevel batteryLevel
84     functions:
85         GoTo gotoRobot
86         Step stepRobot
87     parameters:
88         AutoMovement auto = true
89
90     streams:
91         position: update
92         batteryLevel: update
93
94     gotoRobot.name = "AVG GoTo"
95     stepRobot.name = "AVG Step"
96
97     if batteryLevel < 20: warning("Battery level is below 20%. Load shortly."
98 )
99     if batteryLevel < 10: error("Battery level is below 10%. Please load the
100 battery immediately.")
101
102 }
103
104 interface MobileRobot Walle {}

```

Listing 7.6: Full example of a fictional mobile robot i.e. a six-arm robot mounted on an AVG.